

GHRSSST-PP

*GODAE High Resolution Sea Surface Temperature
Pilot Project*

The 9th Science Team Meeting (G9) of the Global Ocean Data Assimilation Experiment High Resolution Sea Surface Temperature Pilot Project (GHRSSST-PP)

Palais des Congrès in Perros-Guirec, France.

Monday 9th June – Friday 13th June 2008

Final Agenda

Released June 2nd 2008 (C. Donlon/H. Roquet)

Meeting sponsored by:

Welcome note

Hello:

...and welcome to Perros-Guirec, Brittany France and the 9th GHRSS-PP Science Team meeting. This meeting is one of the highlights of the 'SST year' and provides us all with an opportunity to review the health of the GHRSS-PP. On behalf of the GHRSS-PP Science Team I would like to take this opportunity to thank Herve Roquet and the Meteo France team for all of their help and support in preparing the workshop. Thanks also to all the sponsors and you, the participants, who make these important events possible.

The aim of the ninth Science Team meeting is to review progress made within the GHRSS-PP since the last Science Team meeting and prioritise coordination and application activities for the next inter-sessional period.

This meeting marks a significant change in the GHRSS-PP which has successfully demonstrated that high-resolution SST products and services are (a) required and used by the international community and (b) that there is much more that needs to be done to maintain the coordination of the international SST community in terms of the GHRSS Data Processing specification (GDS)-v2.0 (the international consensus 'Manual' for satellite SST data products and services). GHRSS-PP is currently a Pilot Project of the Global Ocean Data Assimilation Experiment (GODAE) which will hold its final symposium in Nice France 12-15th November 2008 (see <http://www.godae.org> for more information). As GODAE will end later this year, the GHRSS-PP, as a pilot Project of GODAE will also conclude. However, following extensive discussions, our work will continue as the **Global High Resolution SST (GHRSS) coordination group** dedicated to maintaining scientific and technical coordination between the international SST community. Our Terms of Reference need to be revised and our work-program updated accordingly and our main focus will be the effective management of the GDS manual and the R/GTS framework.

As the pilot project will conclude, the Editor of the Journal of Operational Oceanography (Proceedings of the Institute of Marine Engineering, Science and Technology (IMarEST)) has suggested that the GHRSS-PP report its progress as a special issue. During the meeting a series of papers will be agreed with a timetable to publication so please bring along your suggestions for papers that celebrate the achievements of the GHRSS-PP over the past 6 years. The JOO would like a wide set of papers covering in situ technologies, satellite, modelling and end applications of SST.

The meeting format is once again biased toward plenary discussion using keynote talks to identify issues. This year we also plan to use poster sessions to reserve more time for breakout discussions. The Palais des Congrès has a nice area at the rear of the Auditorium for posters which can remain in place for the entire meeting. I urge you to bring along your favourite posters including SST applications Please let me know if you intend to do so). We will use parallel session breakout groups to focus the attention of world expertise within the TAG and WG. Breakouts can be difficult to report and the teams should try and support session chairs and rapporteur with sufficient information to provide a report fit for the Workshop proceedings. This format has worked exceptionally well during previous GHRSS-PP workshops and **please come prepared with slides, questions and practical solutions** that can be incorporated into GHRSS-PP plans and specifications. As members of the international Science Team of the GHRSS-PP we all have an obligation to serve the RDAC and GDAC projects with a clear roadmap, based on our collective scientific judgment and consensus opinion to guide and nurture a globally integrated and sustainable high resolution SST operational system for the benefit of all.

Finally, it is with a warm heart that I thank each of you for your contributions, support and dedication to the GHRSS-PP and I look forward to meeting you all once again in France for a productive and stimulating workshop.

Craig Donlon
(Director of the GHRSS-PP International Project Office,
Met Office, Exeter United Kingdom)

1 Preparation

The workshop will focus on the documents listed in Table 1. These documents will form the core of all discussions and should be read prior to meeting. Each document is available from <http://www.ghrsst-pp.org>. The workshop will be mainly plenary discussion and short 10 minute presentations/slides on key issues that are relevant to the meeting are encouraged as a tool for discussion.

Table 1 Document list for the ninth GHRSS-PP Science Team Meeting – all documents are available at <http://www.ghrsst-pp.org/documents.htm?parent=189> unless a dedicated URL is listed.

ID	Title	Author (lead followed by co-authors)	Available on 16/05/08
1	The GHRSS-PP Data Processing Specification v1.0 version 1.6 (GDSv1.6) http://www.ghrsst-pp.org/modules/documents/documents/GDS-v1.0-rev1.6.pdf	C Donlon	x
2	9 th GHRSS-PP Science Team Meeting abstracts	C Donlon/H Roquet	X
3	Report from the GHRSS-PP: 2006/7	C Donlon	X
4	Actions from the 8 th GHRSS-PP Science Team Meeting	C Donlon	X
5	Draft GHRSS-PP Users manual	J Vazquez	x
6	Draft GDS-v2.0 specification/draft text (GDS-TAG), http://www.ghrsst-pp.org/documents.htm?parent=76	C Donlon/K Casey/JF Piolle	x
7	Report from the 8 th GHRSS-PP Science Team meeting http://www.ghrsst-pp.org/modules/documents/documents/GHRSS-PP-VIII-proceedings-v2.2.pdf	C Donlon	X
8	Report from GDAC	J Vazquez/E. Armstrong	
9	Report from the USA RDACs (MISST Project: NAVO, OSDPD, JPL, NRL, RSS RDAC's)	C Gentemann	X
10	Report from the EU RDACs (Medspiration, EUMETSAT OSI-SAF, Met Office, Met.no, DMI, CNR-GOS, NOCS, Marine Core Service)	I. Robinson/H Roquet/C Donlon	
11	Report from Australia	H Beggs/I Barton	X
12	Report from the LTSRF - RAN-TAG	K. Casey/N Rayner	x
13	Report from the SSES/Validation working group	P. LeBorgne/G Corlett	
14	Report from the Diurnal variability working group	C. Merchant	
15	Report from GMPE-TAG (GEO Action DA-06-03)	J Stark/I. Barton	
17	Agenda for the 9 th GHRSS-PP ST Meeting	C Donlon/H. Roquet	x
18	Original Terms of Reference for the GHRSS-PP Science Team	C Donlon	x
19	Report from the HRDDS	David Poulter/Ian Robinson	X
20	Revised Metrics for the GHRSS-PP	Ian Barton/ Gary Corlett	X
21	The GHRSS-PP Multi-Product Ensemble (GMPE) of SST Analyses, Presented at the AGO Ocean Sciences Meeting, Orlando, FL, USA 2 nd March 2008	C Donlon, J Stark and I Barton	X
22	Example paper and template for presenters to report their talks for the GHRSS-PP proceedings	C Donlon/J stark	x

2 Poster Presentations

There is space for posters in the Palais des Congrès and all participants are encouraged to bring poster presentations along to the meeting.

3 Presentations

Please could each presenter provide a **2 page summary** of their presentation by the end of the meeting for inclusion in the GHRSS-PP Proceedings. This will help get the proceedings published efficiently and quickly. A template for your report is provided as Document 22 <https://www.ghrsst-pp.org/modules/documents/documents/Document-22-Example-paper-for%20-proceedings.doc>

4 Guidelines for session leaders

Breakout session Chairs are responsible for coordinating presentations and a local agenda for their session.

4.1 Breakout Session Chairs

Each breakout Session chair is responsible for:

- Preparing the breakout session in advance in order to focus on the key issues for the GHRSS-PP (in the form of questions to be answered and issues to be resolved)
- Arranging short overview presentations and timetabling these to allow as much discussion as possible
- Reporting the session back to plenary on Wednesday morning

- Reporting the session formerly (based on notes from the Rapporteur) as part of the Science Team proceedings in a **written summary report to be delivered by Thursday Evening before you leave the ST meeting** (otherwise experience shows you might not do it at all!)

Breakout sessions are only as good as the reports and plenary presentations that are generated and I urge you to take this part of the breakout session seriously.

4.2 Session Chairs

The main tasks of a session chair are to briefly introduce each speaker, keep the presentations to the time allowed, and to **lead/moderate the discussion after each presentation**. The plenary sessions are your domain and please try to use the General discussion questions above as a guide. Finally, **the chair should work closely with the rapporteur to prepare a short summary of the session**. The report should be of a standard suitable for publication in the Workshop proceedings including appropriate figures and text concluding with the breakout session recommendations.

4.3 Rapporteurs

The purpose of the rapporteurs is **to capture important information during the session for the follow-up of the workshop by the GHRSSST-PO and Science Team**. The rapporteur will be expected to present their reports to the plenary session on Friday afternoon, as a basis for the general discussion and review of the workshop, and for the preparation of conclusions and recommendations for future action GHRSSST-PP.

In preparing your rapporteur reports, you should **avoid making lengthy summaries of the presentations and discussions**. Please try to concentrate on issues which relate directly to the objectives of the workshop, the mandate of GHRSSST-PP and the future development of GHRSSST-PP operational ocean products and services. Your presentation should be short and provide a general overview of the main session outcomes/conclusions rather than a regurgitation of each presentation made. In order to generate a representative report of the meeting, **please can you provide the GHRSSST-PO (C Donlon) with a soft copy of your report by the end of the meeting: this is particularly important for the breakout sessions as the report relies completely on these inputs – what you provide will constitute the final proceedings for these sessions so please, capture as much information as you can. Your inputs will be used as the basis for the conclusions of the 9th Workshop proceedings.**

4.4 WiFi Access

WiFi access at the Palais des Congrès has been arranged for the duration of the meeting. Please see local details at the Palais des Congrès for details of how to make use of this service.

Sunday, 8th May 2008

Time	Agenda item	Session leaders
14:00-17:30	<p>AVHRR data processing meeting Location: Météo-France Centre de Météorologie Spatiale (CMS) in Lannion* (see note hereafter)</p> <p>14:00-16:00 AVHRR processing (general)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Jon Mittaz/ Andy Harris: A recalibration of AVHRR • JF Cayula/ Bruce McKenzie: METOP/AVHRR processing chain at NAVOCEANO • Leon Majewski/Justin Freeman: AVHRR processing chain at BoM • Gerard Legendre: METOP/AVHRR processing chain at MF/CMS <p>16:00-17:30 SSES for AVHRR SST</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • JF Cayula/ Bruce McKenzie: SSES for AVHRR (NAVOCEANO) • Leon Majewski/Justin Freeman: SSES for AVHRR (BoM) • Pierre Le Borgne: SSES for AVHRR (MF/CMS) 	P. Le Borgne
18:30	Informal dinner for those in town in Perros-Guirec. Please email herve.roquet@meteo.fr by 1 June if you would like to attend.	H Roquet/C Donlon

* : for security of access to CMS, only those who have registered their intention to attend beforehand will be admitted; to register, please e-mail Pierre.Leborgne@meteo.fr by Wednesday 4th of June. Transportation from Perros-Guirec will be arranged by P. Le Borgne (mobile : +33 (0)6 76 72 44 49) and H. Roquet (mobile : +33 (0)6 80 34 11 14), leaving Trestraou Beach at 13:30.

Monday, 9th June 2008

Time	Agenda item	Session leaders
08-30	Registration & Coffee: Location Palais des Congrès in Perros-Guirec	
08:45	Welcome and logistics	H Roquet
08:50	Welcome address from Pascale Delecluse, Deputy Director of Research, Météo-France	
09:20	Review of 9 th ST meeting Agenda	Chair: C Donlon Rapporteur: Ken Casey
09:25	Report from the GHRSS-PP International project Office <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Overview of the GHRSS-PP project status, priorities and aims of the Workshop. Review action items since the 8th GHRSS-PP Science Team Meeting 	
10:00	Coffee	
Session 1. R/GTS Components: Reports to the GHRSS-PP Science Team		
10:20	Global Data Assembly Centre (GDAC) report and PO.DAAC report: J Vazquez et al.	Chair: Gary Wick Rapporteur: Ken Casey
10:50	Long-Term Stewardship and Re-analysis Facility (LTSRF) report : Kenneth S Casey	
11:10	USA (MISST) report: Chelle Gentemann	
11:30	Europe (Medspiration + MCS + OSI-SAF) report: J-F Piollé	
11:50	Australia (BLUElink<>) report: Helen Beggs	
12:10	GHRSS-PP Multi-Product Ensemble (GMPE) TAG Report: Ian Barton & John Stark	
12:30	Lunch	
14:00	Diurnal Variability Technical Advisory Group (DV-WG) report: Chris Merchant	Chair: Gary Wick Rapporteur: Ken Casey
14:20	SSES/Validation working group (SSES-Val-WG) report: Pierre LeBorgne & Gary Corlett	
14:40	HRDDS system report: David Poulter	
15:00	The JCOMM Pilot Project for the WMO Integrated Global Observing Systems (WIGOS), Etienne Charpentier	
15:30	Tea	
15:50	Future plans of EUMETSAT for GHRSS-PP: Hans Bonekamp	Chair: G Wick Rapporteur: Ken Casey
16:10	Future plans of ESA for GHRSS-PP: Olivier Arino	
16:30	SST-Activities in the framework of GOOS-AFRICA, Raymond	
16:50	GHRSS-PP Data Processing Specification v2.0 (GDS-TAG) report: C Donlon Plenary discussion: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Identification of priority issues for the 9th workshop (C Donlon) Agreement of Breakout group membership 	
17:45	Close	
17:45+	Posters can be put up in the Palais des Congrès	
18:30	Welcome address by the Mayor of Perros-Guirec, Y. Bonnot, and icebreaker cocktail offered by the City of Perros Guirec. An opportunity to meet everyone and to exchange ideas and plan for the week ahead.	

Tuesday, 10th June 2008

Time	Agenda item			Session leaders
Session 2. Parallel breakout sessions				
Parallel session				
09:00	BG-1: GHRSSST Data Processing Specification (GDS) TAG Chair: C Donlon (craig.donlon@metoffice.gov.uk) Rapporteur: JF Piolle Please contact the Chair to arrange a presentation Location: Palais des Congrès	BG-2: GHRSSST L4 Multi-Product Ensemble (GMPE) TAG Chair: Ian Barton/John Stark (ian.barton@csiro.au , john.stark@metoffice.gov.uk) Rapporteur: John Stark Please contact the Chair to arrange a presentation Location: Palais des Congrès	BG-3: Diurnal Variability TAG Chair: Chris Merchant (c.merchant@ed.ac.uk) Rapporteur: Gary Wick Please contact the Chair to arrange a presentation Location: Palais des Congrès	Breakout Groups-1
10:30	Coffee			
Parallel session				
11:00	BG-1: GHRSSST Data Processing Specification (GDS) TAG Chair: C Donlon (craig.donlon@metoffice.gov.uk) Rapporteur: JF Piolle Please contact the Chair to arrange a presentation Location: Palais des Congrès	BG-2: GHRSSST L4 Multi-Product Ensemble (GMPE) TAG Chair: Ian Barton/John Stark (ian.barton@csiro.au , john.stark@metoffice.gov.uk) Rapporteur: John Stark Please contact the Chair to arrange a presentation Location: Palais des Congrès	BG-3: Diurnal Variability TAG Chair: Chris Merchant (c.merchant@ed.ac.uk) Rapporteur: Gary Wick Please contact the Chair to arrange a presentation Location: Palais des Congrès	Breakout Groups-1
12:30	Lunch			
Parallel session				
14:00	BG-1: GHRSSST Data Processing Specification (GDS) TAG Chair: C Donlon (craig.donlon@metoffice.gov.uk) Rapporteur: JF Piolle Please contact the Chair to arrange a presentation Location: Palais des Congrès	BG-4: Reanalysis Project (RAN-TAG) Chair: Ken Casey (kenneth.casey@noaa.gov) Rapporteur: Nick Rayner/ Tess Brandon Please contact the Chair to arrange a presentation Location: Palais des Congrès	BG-5: SSES-Validation WG Chair: Pierre Le Borgne (Pierre.Leborgne@meteo.fr) Rapporteur: Gary Corlett Please contact the Chair to arrange a presentation Location: Palais des Congrès/MF	Breakout Groups-2
16:00	Tea			
Parallel session				
16:30	BG-1: GHRSSST Data Processing Specification (GDS) TAG Chair: C Donlon (craig.donlon@metoffice.gov.uk) Rapporteur: JF Piolle Please contact the Chair to arrange a presentation Location: Palais des Congrès	BG-4: Reanalysis Project (RAN-TAG) Chair: Ken Casey (kenneth.casey@noaa.gov) Rapporteur: Nick Rayner/Tess Brandon Please contact the Chair to arrange a presentation Location: Palais des Congrès	BG-5: SSES-Validation WG Chair: Pierre Le Borgne (Pierre.Leborgne@meteo.fr) Rapporteur: Gary Corlett Please contact the Chair to arrange a presentation Location: Palais des Congrès/MF	Breakout Groups-2
17:30	Close			
17:30-19:30	Dedicated Poster Session with aperitif in the Palais des Congrès			
18:30-19:30	MyOcean SST-TAC planning meeting in the Palais des Congrès			

Breakout group draft agendas

<p>BG-1: GHRSS-PP Data Processing Specification (GDS) TAG session preliminary agenda (All Day)</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Introduction (Aim of the day (to complete and agree the GDS-2.0) 2. Key Issues for GDS-v2.0 3. File Metadata, netCDF CF1.3, grid schemes fro L2P, L3P, L4 and GMPE 4. Issues and consensus on L2P and L2Pc 5. Issues and consensus on L3P 6. Issues and consensus on L4 7. Issues and consensus on GMPE L4+ products 8. Preparation of breakout report 9. Writing tasks and key actions 10. 	<p>BG-2: GHRSS-PP L4 Multi-Product Ensemble (GMPE) TAG</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Introduction and the current system (Barton / Stark) 2. BoM analysis and intercomparisons / validation (Beggs) 3. Analysis error / temporal and spatial representativity (Reynolds) 4. Jmin / other objective metrics (Cummings) 5. ODYSSEA intercomparisons and metrics (Piolle / Tournadre /Autret) 7. Broad scale climate metrics such as ENSO / NAO (Stark) 8. Small scale intercomparison (Poulter ?) 9. Operational analysis validation and intercomparison (McKenzie /May / Grumbine ?) 10. Input from Japan, such as Kuroshio comparison / metrics. 	<p>BG-3: Diurnal Variability TAG Session 1 (0900-1030) (i) Updates on recent work (10 min presentations):</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Chelle Gentemann: Large DV events 2. Andy Harris: Global DV prediction using turbulence models 3. Pierre Le Borgne: Geostationary-derived DV fields 4. Dave Poulter: Automated identification of DV events 5. Helen Beggs: RAMSAA SST analysis: two DV mitigation methods 6. Chris Merchant: Initial experiments in DV analysis <p>(ii) Open discussion of presentations and science progress</p> <p>Session 2 (1100-1230) (iii) Future plans and co-ordination of DVWG activities A structured discussion covering</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> * Review of actions * Priorities for next year * Review upcoming funded projects * Identify gaps relative to priorities * Review and revised plans for co-ordinated initiatives <ul style="list-style-type: none"> models-data intercomparison hi-res tropical data set operational ALADIN+ * Meetings & Joint publications
<p>BG-4: Reanalysis Project (RAN-TAG)</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Introduction and Overview - Ken Casey 2. Rapid Review of Relevant Projects 3. Prioritization of Questions/Issues 4. Discussion of Questions/Issues in Priority Order 	<p>BG-5: SSES and Validation working group session preliminary agenda.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. 14:00 Introduction to GHRSS-PP Validation Group (Gary Corlett) 2. 14:10 REMSS current SSES (Chelle Gentemann) 3. 14:20 BoM current SSES (Leon Majewski) 4. 14:30 Navoceanoo current SSES (Doug May/Bruce McKenzie) 5. 14:40 NOAA current SSES (Andy Harris) 6. 14:50 MODIS current SSES (Bob Evans) 7. 15:00 AATSR current SSES (Gary Corlett) 8. 15:10 OSISAF current SSES (Pierre Le Borgne) 9. 15:20 Alternate SSES schemes (Pierre Tandeo) 10. 15:30 Discussion on SSES 11. 16:00 Coffee break 12. 16:30 CEOS guidelines (David Llewellyn-Jones) 13. 16:40 Validation tools - Kepler (Peter Cornillon) 14. 16:50 Validation in Arctic conditions (Steinar Eastwood/Dave Poulter) 15. 17:00 METOP SST Validation (Anne Marsouin) 16. 17:10 Discussion on validation 17:30 Close 	

Wednesday, 11th June 2008

Time	Agenda item	Session leaders
Session 3. Reports from Breakout Sessions and discussion		
08:30	Breakout report from DV-WG: Chris Merchant and Gary Wick	Chair: Peter Cornillon Rapporteur: Helen Beggs
09:00	Breakout report from GMPE-TAG: John Stark & Ian Barton	
09:30	Breakout report from GDS-TAG: Craig Donlon & Jean Francios Piolle	
10:00	Coffee	
11:00	Breakout report from the RAN-TAG: Ken Casey, Nick Rayner & Tess Brandon	Chair: Peter Cornillon Rapporteur: Helen Beggs
11:30	Breakout report from the SSES-Val TAG: Pierre LeBorgne and Gary Corlett	
12:00	Close	
13:45	Visit to the Seven Islands (natural reserve) sponsored by EUMETSAT OSI-SAF and Météo-France	
19:30	Conference Dinner Sponsored by the European Space Agency (ESA)	

Thursday, 12th June 2008

Time	Agenda item	Session leaders
Session 4: Applications using GHRSS-PP data products		
(a) New data/methods/Products		
(b) NWP, Operational Oceanography, Hurricanes etc.		
(c) General SST Science		
08:30	Inter-sensor and multi-algorithm comparison of the Adriatic satellite-derived SST , Igor tomazic and Milivoj Kuzmic	
08:45	High Latitude level 4 SST products at DMI , Jacob L Høyer	
09:00	L4 Sea Surface Temperature applications at Mercator Ocean , Silvana Ramos Buarque et al	Chair: Chelle Gentemann Rapporteur: Dave Poulter
09:15	The Mercator Océan forecasting systems in the MyOcean context: towards the use of High Resolution Sea Surface Temperature products , L. Parent, E. Dombrowsky, N. Ferry and C.E. Testut	
09:30	Using optimal estimation methods for sea surface temperature , Chris Merchant	
09:45	Multi-sensor Ultra-high Resolution (MUR) data-fusion methodology , Chin T. M. et al	
10:00	GCOS SST/SI Inter-comparison Framework for Global SST Analyses , Tess B. Brandon and Kenneth S. Casey	
10:15	Small-scale variability and observational error estimates for gridded analyses of SST data , Alexey Kaplan	
10:30	Coffee	
11:00	An assessment on using the new multi-instrument SST analysis when making operational marine weather warnings and forecasts , Joe Sienkiewicz	Chair: Chelle Gentemann Rapporteur: Dave Poulter
11:15	Inter-comparisons among Global Daily SST Analyses , Richard W. Reynolds	
11:30	Operational High Resolution Sea Ice and SST Analysis at NCEP , Robert Grumbine	
11:45	Merging Satellite Infrared and Microwave Sea Surface Temperature in the China Seas , Lei Guan, Yanzhen Wang, Heng Liu and Hui Zhang	
12:00	The CNR regional Optimally Interpolated SST products from MERSEA to MyOcean: new re-analyses and future operational products , B. Buongiorno Nardelli et al	
12:15	Recent Developments with the OSTIA SST Analysis , John Stark and Craig Donlon	
12:30	Lunch	
14:00	Future plans of JAXA for GHRSS-PP : Kachi Misako	Chair: Rapporteur: Dave Poulter
14:15	L2P operations at ESA , N. Houghton	
14:30	A new generation of SEVIRI products , Pierre Le Borgne et al	
14:45	Improvements to the NOAA Geostationary SST products , John Mittaz, Andy Harris and Eileen Maturi	
15:00	The AVHRR GHRSS Reprocessing Project and Accessing GHRSS Data from Matlab , Peter Cornillon et al.	
15:15	The GMES Marine Core Service MyOcean project and its SST Thematic Assembly Centre (SST-TAC) , H. Roquet, C. Donlon, J.-F. Piolle, B. Buongiorno Nardelli, S. Eastwood, D. Poulter, and J Hoeyer	
15:30	Tea	
16:00	Potential of existing SST products to quantify upper ocean mesoscale dynamics , F Collard et al.	Chair: Rapporteur: Dave Poulter
16:15	SST changes in the Mediterranean Sea from 1985 to 2006 , Leo Nykjaer	
16:30	Impact of resolving the diurnal SST cycle from satellite data in describing the mean state and variability of West African Monsoon circulation , S. Marullo, A. Dell'Aquila, P. Ruti	
17:00	Mean seasonal cycles and variability in SST at French coastal stations observed from in situ and satellite data , Bertrand Saulquin and Francis Gohin.	
17:15	Datacasting: Informed Pull of GHRSS Data using Really Simple Syndication (RSS) , A Bingham et al	
17:30	Close	
18:00-19:30	GHRSS-PP Advisory Council meeting. Location Palais des Congrès (Chair: K Casey, NOAA NODC)	

Friday, 13th June 2008

Time	Agenda item	Session leaders
Session 4 (Cont.)		
08:30	A sea surface temperature climatology from (A)ATSR data for climate change research, Owen Embury and Chris Merchant	Chair: Craig Donlon
08:45	Bias Correction of AVHRR Pathfinder data against (A)ATSR to produce a satellite SST record from 1982 to 2007, Tom Blackmore	Rapporteur: Peter Cornillon
Session 5 GDS-v2.0		
09:00	GHRSSST GDS-2.0 Metrics, G Corlett and I Barton	Chair: Craig Donlon
09:30	General discussion of the GDS-v2.0	Rapporteur: Peter Cornillon
10:30	Coffee	
Session 6 Review of action items		
11:00	Review of Action list from the 9 th GHRSSST-PP Science Team Meeting and outstanding actions from 8 th Science Team Meeting	Chair: Craig Donlon Rapporteur: Peter Cornillon
Session 7 Close of the Pilot Project and Start of the Coordination Group		
12:00	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Close of the GHRSSST Pilot Project 2. Start of the GHRSSST Coordination Group 3. Review of GHRSSST Coordination Group ToR 4. Science Team Membership (New nominations and Resignations to be passed to the Chair by Thursday 17th June) 	Chair: Craig Donlon Rapporteur: Peter Cornillon
12:30	Lunch	
Session 8 Final discussion, Wrap up session and close		
14:00	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Summary of workshop 2. Special issue of the Journal of Operational Oceanography, B McKenzie, C Donlon and Ralph Rayner 3. Preparation of proceedings: Chair & Rapporteur inputs 4. Next meeting location and dates 5. AOB 	Chair: C Donlon Rapporteur: John Stark
15:30	Thank you and close of meeting	

Appendix I Draft Terms of Reference for a GDS-2.0 Working group

Preamble

The GHRSSST-PP data Processing Specification (GDS) v1.7 has been developed by the GHRSSST-PP science Team over the past 5 years and was recently reviewed by the GDS Technical Advisory Group (GDS-TAG). The GDS is now composed of distinct sections written as separate documents. There is a need to transition the GDS v1.7 into a GDS-v2.0 which captures the following basic elements:

- Full descriptions of L2P data streams including input/output definition, QC and formatting of products
- Full description gridded products (L3P) including input/output definition, QC and formatting of products
- Revised metadata frameworks for netCDF and the MMR system as appropriate
- Operational system messaging including comprehensive error and service metrics
- Better more homogeneous and well described SSES
- Definition and provision of new data sets (e.g., METOP, MTSAT)
- A full revision of L4 and L2P data set content and format based on user feedback and commitments
- Better focus of Sea Ice (concentration and extent) and SST in the marginal ice zone
- Implementation of improved schemes to account for diurnal variability in a way that provides users with a useful and error-bound product using other data sets in synergy (e.g., Ocean Colour and NWP outputs)
- Improved ancillary data and dynamic flags tuned to individual satellite sensors
- Implementation, operation and validation of the HR-DDS system
- Implementation, operation and validation of the MDB system
- Implementation, operation and validation of generic RDAC systems
- Implementation, operation and validation of generic GDAC systems
- Implementation, operation and validation of generic LTSRF systems

Other issues not covered by this list should be considered by the team as appropriate to the vision of GDS-v2.0.

Terms of Reference

The GDS-2.0 Working group are requested by the GHRSSST-PP science Team to:

1. During the 8th GHRSSST-PP Science Team identify issues that need to be resolved by the development of the GDSv2.0.
2. Bearing in mind the discussions at the GHRSSST-PP 8th ST Workshop, propose a simple plan of action for development and production of the GDS v2.0 to be completed by the start of 2008
3. Present a summary report of findings to the GHRSSST-PP science Team at the end of the 8th Science Team Workshop.

Membership

Chair:

Co-Chair:

Members (up to 6)

Appendix-II Provisional attendance list (Please pass corrections to the GHRSS-PP for update)

Armstrong, Edward
Jet Propulsion Laboratory/California Institute of
Technology
300/320 4800 Oak Grove Dr.
Pasadena, California
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How to find out more about the GHRSSST-PP:

A complete description of the GHRSSST-PP together with all project documentation can be found at the following web spaces:

GHRSSST-PP	http://www.ghrsst-pp.org
Medspiration	http://www.medspiration.org
BLUElink>	http://www.bluelink.au
MISST	http://www.misst.org
NGSST	http://www.ocean.caos.tohoku.jp
GHRSSST-PP GDAC	http://ghrsst.jpl.nasa.gov
GHRSSST-PP LTSRF	http://ghrsst.nodc.noaa.gov
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